

Synthesis of some 2-Heterocyclphenothiazines as Potential Anti-inflammatory Agents

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Twenty-six compounds belonging to five different series (1-5), namely, 2-(2-alkyl- or aryl-4-thiazolyl)- and 2-(2-amino- or substituted-amino-4-thiazolyl)phenothiazines (1 and 2, respectively), their 10-acetyl analogues (3), 2-(2-amino-6-aryl-4-pyrimidinyl)- and 2-(5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-3-pyrazolyl)-phenothiazines (4 and 5, respectively) have been synthesised through different routes. 1 and 2 were synthesised by the condensation of 2-chloroacetylphenothiazine (7) with various thioamides and thioureas, respectively, and 3 by reacting 10-acetyl analogue of 7 with thioureas. Compounds 4 were prepared by the reaction of the chalcones (9) with guanidine carbonate in the presence of NaOH and 5 by treating 9 with hydrazine hydrate in AcOH. Compounds 1-5 exhibited mild anti-inflammatory activity except 2, $R_2 = 4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$, which showed significant activity.

PROMPTED by the significant anti-inflammatory activity exhibited by a series of 2-(2-amino- and substituted-amino-4-thiazolyl)benzothiazoles¹ and 2'-amino- and substituted-amino-4-aryl-2,4'-bithiazolyls², we thought it of interest to synthesise analogous series of compounds incorporating S,N-containing phenothiazinyl moiety in place of thiazole and benzothiazole nuclei, namely, 2-(2-alkyl- or

Scheme 1: Reagents: (i) Dilute HCl-AcOH, (ii) R_2CSNH_2 in acetone, (iii) $\text{NH}_2\text{CSNHR}_2$ in acetone, (iv) $\text{NH}_2\text{CSNHR}_2$ in ethanol, (v) aqueous NaOH at $<10^\circ$, (vi) $(\text{NH}_2\text{C(=NH)NH}_2)_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{CO}_2$ in ethanol, aqueous NaOH, (vii) $\text{NH}_2\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in ethanol-AcOH.

aryl-4-thiazolyl)- and 2-(2-amino- or substituted-amino-4-thiazolyl)-phenothiazines (1 and 2, respectively) and their 10-acetyl analogues (3). Following the reports of good anti-inflammatory activity exhibited by mono- and di-cyclic pyrimidines³ and pyrazolines⁴, two series of 2-(2-amino-6-aryl-4-pyri-

midinyl)- and 2-(5-aryl-4,5-dihydro-3-pyrazolyl)-phenothiazines (4 and 5, respectively) were also synthesised for evaluation as potential anti-inflammatory agents. The above series of compounds have been synthesised following the reaction sequence outlined in Scheme 1.

2-Chloroacetyl-10-acetylphenothiazine (6) and 2-chloroacetylphenothiazine (7) were prepared according to literature procedure⁵. Condensation of 7 with thioacetamide or thiobenzamide in refluxing acetone gave 2-(2-methyl- or phenyl-4-thiazolyl)-phenothiazines (1) according to Hantzsch thiazole synthesis⁶. Other thiobenzamides substituted in the benzene ring failed to react under similar conditions even on prolonged refluxing. Ethanol could not be used as a reaction solvent due to low solubility of 7 and use of higher boiling solvents resulted in decomposition of 7. In contrast to the failure of substituted-thiobenzamides to react with 7, condensation of thiourea and *N*-substituted alkyl- and aryl-thioureas proceeded smoothly in refluxing acetone to yield 2-(2-amino- or substituted-amino-4-thiazolyl)phenothiazines (2) in good yields (40–90%). Similarly, 2-chloroacetyl-10-acetylphenothiazine (6) reacted with thiourea and phenylthiourea in refluxing ethanol furnishing 3 in excellent yields.

The ir spectra of all the compounds of series 2 displayed two or three sharp bands in the region 3 350–3 100 cm^{-1} due to stretching absorption of amino group and phenothiazine with a strong band at $\sim 1 620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to NH bending. The spectra of 1 showed only one sharp peak at $\sim 3 350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to NH stretch of phenothiazine moiety. The ir spectra of 3 exhibited a sharp peak at $\sim 1 670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O str. of 10-acetyl group) in addition to peaks at 3 400, 3 300 and 3 180 cm^{-1} (NH str.) and another at $\sim 1 625 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH bend.). The pmr spectra of 3 displayed characteristic signal of three proton intensity at $\delta 2.20$ (CH_3 of acetyl group) apart from signals in the aromatic region.

The chalcones (9) were obtained by the conventional Claisen–Schmidt reaction on condensation of 2-acetylphenothiazine (8) with various aromatic aldehydes in ethanol in the presence of aqueous NaOH (yield 80–84%). Reaction of the chalcones (9) with guanidine carbonate in ethanol in the presence of aqueous NaOH gave the 2-aminopyrimidines (4) in 57–68% yield according to the procedure reported by El-Rayyes⁷. The ir spectra of 9 showed strong bands at $\sim 3 310$ (NH str.), 1 650 (C=O str.) and 1 590 cm^{-1} (C=C str. or NH bend.). The spectra of 4 displayed three bands at 3 480–3 100 cm^{-1} due to stretching absorption of NH and NH_2 groups with strong bands at 1 630–1 610 (C=N str. or NH bend.) and $\sim 1 580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=C str.). The pmr spectra of 4 were in conformity with their structures.

The chalcones have been reported to react with hydrazine and phenylhydrazine in acetic acid to yield the pyrazolines through hydrazones as inter-

mediates⁸. In the present work, 4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazolines (5) have been synthesised by treating the chalcones (9) with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solutions in presence of acetic acid. The ir spectra of 5 showed prominent peaks at 3 300–3 260 (NH stretch) and 1 630–1 600 cm^{-1} (NH bend. or C=N stretch). The pmr spectra of 5 exhibited peaks at $\delta 3.00$ – 3.20 (1H, dd, CH_2 of pyrazoline ring), 3.60–3.80 (1H, dd, CH_2 of pyrazoline ring), 4.80–5.10 (1H, dd, CH of pyrazoline ring) and 6.8–8.1 (ArH, m and NH). Integration of signals at $\delta 3.1$ – 5.2 indicated the presence of three protons forming an ABX system corresponding to CH– CH_2 group of pyrazoline ring.

Anti-inflammatory activity: Selected compounds belonging to all the five series (1–5) were subjected to preliminary screening for anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenin-induced rat paw edema test according to the procedure of Winter *et al.*⁹ as modified by Srimal and Dhawan¹⁰. The activity in terms of percentage inhibition at a dose level of 1/5th of ALD_{50} of the compound was determined. Indomethacin used as standard showed 40–50% inhibition at a dose of 2 mg/kg. ALD_{50} values of all the compounds tested were more than 1000 mg/kg in mice. Compounds of the type 1 and 2 showed only mild activity ($\leq 20\%$ inhibition) except 2j which showed 40.5% inhibition. The presence of acetyl group at position-10 of the phenothiazine (3) does not appear to have any effect on the activity and they possess activity of the same order as the parent compound in series 1. Compounds in series 4 and 5 showed only mild activity (inhibition $\sim 20\%$). Three chalcones (9) tested were found to be inactive.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Perkin–Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra at 70 eV on a MS-12 instrument equipped with a direct inlet system, source temperature being kept around 165°.

2-(2-Methyl-4-thiazolyl)phenothiazine (1; $R_1 = \text{CH}_3$): Thioacetamide (0.75 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (40 ml) was added to a solution of 2-chloroacetylphenothiazine (2.75 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (50 ml) and the mixture heated under reflux. A crystalline solid began to separate after 4 h. After refluxing for another 4 h, the reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the residue washed thoroughly with NaHCO_3 solution (2%), then with water, dried and crystallised from methanol, (1.6 g, 54%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 64.6; H, 4.0; N, 9.0. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires: C, 64.9; H, 4.1; N, 9.4%); ν_{max} 3 360 (NH str.), 1 620 (NH bend.); m/z 296 (M^+); (Calcd.: 296).

1 ($R_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$): was prepared in a similar manner and crystallised from ethanol, (44%), m.p. 243° (Found: C, 70.1; H, 4.4; N, 7.5. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$

requires: C, 70.4; H, 3.9; N, 7.8%); ν_{\max} 3 350 cm^{-1} (NH str.).

2-(2-Amino- or substituted amino-4-thiazolyl)phenothiazines (2). A typical preparation of 2-[2-(*p*-toluidino)-4-thiazolyl]phenothiazine (2, $R_2 = 4\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$): A solution of 2-chloroacetylphenothiazine (7; 2.75 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-tolylthiourea (1.66 g, 0.01 mol) in dry acetone (50 ml) was heated under reflux. A crystalline solid separated after 1 h. After refluxing for another 3 h and cooling, the solid was filtered, washed with acetone and treated with NaHCO_3 solution (2%) overnight. The resulting solid product, was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol-water, (2e; 2.4 g, 62%), m.p. 209° (Found: C, 67.9; H, 4.6; N, 10.8. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{OS}_2$ requires: C, 68.2; H, 4.4; N, 10.8%); ν_{\max} 3 350, 3 300 (NH str.), 1 610 cm^{-1} (NH bend.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.1 (2H, s, NH), 6.7–7.6 (12H, m, ArH).

Other compounds of series 2 were prepared similarly (Table 1).

2-(2-Amino-4-thiazolyl)-10-acetylphenothiazine (3; R=H): A mixture of 2-chloroacetyl-10-acetylphenothiazine (6; 3.17 g, 0.01 mol), thiourea (0.76 g, 0.01 mol) and ethanol (40 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h and then allowed to stand overnight. The separated solid was filtered, washed with NaHCO_3 solution (2%), then with water, dried and crystallised from acetone/ethanol, (3.0 g, 88%), m.p. 202° (Found: C, 60.3; H, 3.7; N, 12.2. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{OS}_2$ requires: C, 60.2; H, 3.8; N, 12.4%); ν_{\max} 3 400, 3 300, 3 180 (NH $_2$ str.), 1 670 (C=O str.), 1 630 cm^{-1} (NH bend.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.20 (3H, s, COCH_3), 5.75 (2H, bs, NH $_2$), 7.3–8.25 (8H, m, ArH); m/z 339 (M^+), (Calcd. 339).

3 ($R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) was prepared similarly, (89%), m.p. 208° (Found: C, 66.0; H, 3.9; N, 9.7. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{OS}_2$ requires: C, 66.5; H, 4.1; N, 10.1%); ν_{\max} 3 080 (NH str.), 1 665 (C=O str.), 1 625 cm^{-1} (NH bend.).

1-(2-Phenothiazinyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (9): A typical preparation of 1-(2-phenothiazinyl)-3-(*p*-anisyl)-2-propen-1-one (9c; $R_3 = 4\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$): To a cooled (5–10°) and stirred solution of 2-acetylphenothiazine (8; 2.41 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-anisaldehyde (1.36 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added aqueous NaOH solution (0.7 g/1 ml) dropwise during a period of 20 min. The reaction mixture was stirred further for 6 h at 25° and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (2.80 g, 78%), m.p. 202° (Found: C, 73.4; H, 5.1; N, 3.8. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ requires: C, 73.5; H, 4.7; N, 3.9%); ν_{\max} 3 320 (NH str.), 1 650 (C=O str.), 1 590 cm^{-1} (C=C str. or NH bend.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.6 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.75–7.50 (13H, m, ArH and C=CH), 8.7 (1H, s, NH); m/z 359 (M^+), (Calcd. 359).

The other chalcones (9) in the series were prepared similarly (Table 2).

2-(2-Amino-6-aryl-4-pyrimidinyl)phenothiazines (4). A typical synthesis: To a refluxing mixture of 9c (3.59 g, 0.01 mol) and guanidine carbonate (1.80 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added an aqueous solution of NaOH (40%; 5 ml) portionwise during a period of 3 h. Refluxing was continued for further 6 h and the separated solid on cooling was filtered, washed with cold ethanol followed by water, dried and crystallised from DMF-water, (4c; 2.27 g, 57%), m.p. 245° (Found: C, 69.7; H, 4.8; N, 14.0. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$ requires: C, 69.4;

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(2-AMINO- OR SUBSTITUTED-AMINO-4-THIAZOLYL)PHENOTHIAZINES (2)

Compd. no.*	R_2	M.p. °C	Yield** %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
2a	H	227	90 ^a	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$	60.2 (60.6)	3.4 (3.7)	14.0 (14.1)
2b	C_6H_5	264	61 ^b	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$	62.5 (62.8)	4.4 (4.6)	12.6 (12.9)
2c	$\text{CH}_3\text{-OH=CH}_2$	117	89°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$	64.3 (64.1)	4.3 (4.5)	12.5 (12.5)
2d	C_6H_5	201	64°	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$	67.1 (67.6)	3.8 (4.0)	11.1 (11.3)
2e	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	209	62 ^d	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$	67.9 (68.2)	4.6 (4.4)	10.8 (10.8)
2f	4- FC_6H_4	218	61°	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{FN}_3\text{S}_2$	64.1 (64.5)	3.3 (3.6)	10.9 (10.7)
2g	4- ClC_6H_4	214	70 ^b	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_3\text{S}_2$	61.7 (61.8)	3.0 (3.4)	10.1 (10.3)
2h	2- ClC_6H_4	188	40°	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_3\text{S}_2$	61.5 (61.8)	3.3 (3.4)	10.3 (10.3)
2i	4- BrC_6H_4	212	57°	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrN}_3\text{S}_2$	55.4 (55.8)	3.3 (3.1)	9.7 (9.3)
2j	4- $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$	> 300	84°	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$	63.7 (64.0)	3.5 (3.9)	10.0 (9.7)

*2c: m/z 337 (M^+), (Calcd. 337); 2d: m/z 373 (M^+), (Calcd. 373). **Solvent of crystallisation: ^aacetone, ^bmethanol, ^cethanol, ^daqueous ethanol.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-(2-PHENOTHIAZINYL)-3-ARYL-2-PROPEN-1-ONES (9)

Compd.* no.	R ₂	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
9a	C ₆ H ₅	163	82	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ NOS	76.2 (76.6)	4.3 (4.6)	3.9 (4.3)
9b	4-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	170	84	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ NOS	76.9 (77.0)	4.9 (5.0)	4.2 (4.1)
9c	4-OH ₂ OC ₆ H ₄	202	78	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	73.4 (73.5)	5.1 (4.7)	3.8 (3.9)
9d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	212	71	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ClNOS	69.5 (69.3)	3.9 (3.8)	3.7 (3.8)
9e	2-Furyl	195	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ NO ₂ S	71.3 (71.5)	4.0 (4.1)	4.2 (4.4)
9f	2-Thienyl	191	83	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ NOS ₂	68.5 (68.1)	4.0 (3.9)	4.1 (4.2)

*9a : *m/z* 329 (*M*⁺), (Calcd. 329) ; 9f : *m/z* 335 (*M*⁺), (Calcd. 335). **All compounds recrystallised from acetic acid.

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(2-AMINO-6-ARYL-4-PYRIMIDINYL)PHENOTHIAZINES (4)

Compd.* no.	R ₂	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
4a	C ₆ H ₅	235	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	72.0 (71.7)	4.5 (4.3)	15.6 (15.2)
4b	4-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185	59	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	72.1 (72.3)	4.8 (4.7)	14.5 (14.7)
4c	4-OH ₂ OC ₆ H ₄	245	57	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS	69.7 (69.4)	4.8 (4.5)	14.0 (14.1)
4d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	275	57	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ S	66.0 (65.6)	3.2 (3.7)	13.7 (13.9)
4e	2-Furyl	232	61	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS	66.9 (67.0)	3.8 (3.9)	15.3 (15.6)
4f	2-Thienyl	240	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂	64.5 (64.2)	4.2 (3.7)	14.9 (15.0)

*4b : *m/z* 382 (*M*⁺), (Calcd. 382) ; 4d : *m/z* 402/404 (*M*⁺), (Calcd. 402/404). **All compounds recrystallised from DMF-H₂O.

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(5-ARYL-4,5-DIHYDRO-3-PYRAZOLYL)PHENOTHIAZINES (5)

Compd.* no.	R ₂	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
5a	C ₆ H ₅	205	63	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	73.1 (73.5)	5.4 (5.0)	12.0 (12.2)
5b	4-OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	165	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ S	73.6 (74.0)	5.2 (5.3)	11.4 (11.8)
5c	4-OH ₂ OC ₆ H ₄	193	62	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₃ OS	71.0 (70.8)	4.8 (5.1)	11.4 (11.3)
5d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	250	58	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	67.0 (66.8)	3.9 (4.2)	10.9 (11.1)
5e	2-Furyl	208	64	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	68.1 (68.5)	4.2 (4.5)	12.2 (12.6)
5f	2-Thienyl	215	63	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	65.6 (65.3)	4.4 (4.3)	12.0 (12.0)

*5a : *m/z* 343 (*M*⁺), (Calcd. 343) ; 5f : *m/z* 349 (*M*⁺), (Calcd. 349). **All compounds crystallised from DMF-H₂O.

H, 4.5 ; N, 14.1%) ; ν_{\max} 3 460, 3 340, 3 160 (NH str.), 1 630 (C=N str. or NH bend.), 1 580 cm⁻¹ (C=C str.) ; δ (DMSO-d₆) 4.1 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.2–8.3 (15H, m, ArH and NH) ; *m/z* 398 (*M*⁺), (Calcd. 398).

Other compounds in the series (4) were prepared similarly (Table 3).

2-(5-Aryl-4,5-dihydro-3-pyrazolyl)phenothiazines (5).
A typical procedure : To a solution of the chalcone

(9c ; 3.59 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added hydrazine hydrate (0.75 g, 0.015 mol). The mixture was refluxed gently on a water-bath for 4 h. After cooling, the separated solid was filtered, washed with a little ethanol followed by water, dried and crystallised from DMF-water, (5c ; 2.3 g, 62%), m. p. 193° (Found : C, 71.0 ; H, 4.8 ; N, 11.4. C₂₂H₁₆N₃OS requires : C, 70.8 ; H, 5.1 ; N, 11.3%) ; ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH str.), 1 605 cm⁻¹ (C=N str. or NH

bend.) ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.0–3.8 (5H, m, OCH₃ and CH₂ of pyrazoline ring), 4.85 (1H, dd, pyrazoline proton at position-5) and 6.7–8.5 (13H, m, ArH and NH) ; m/z 373 (M^+), (Calcd. 373).

The other members of the series (5) were prepared similarly (Table 4).

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